

The Impact of Cost Control Strategies on Companies' Performance and Growth: Evidence from Some Selected Companies in Zimbabwe

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ Professor Kong Yushang ⁽²⁾ Wayne Chipwere (Corresponding Author) ⁽³⁾ Joseph Adu-Gyamfi
⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾⁽³⁾ Affiliation: Jiangsu University, School of Finance and Economics

Abstract

The study investigated the effect of cost management on the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Zimbabwe. The specific objectives include examining the cost of inventories, the cost of labour, and the cost of sales on performance. The study will be relevant for investors, management board and regulatory bodies. The study employed a descriptive research design. The study employed panel data covering four (4) years 2014-2018 which was gathered from the financial statement of a selected manufacturing firm. The study employed the pooled regression analysis for its data analysis. The study revealed that cost of inventories has insignificant positive effect on return on equity, which depicts that cost on inventories have a positive influence of the going concern of the organization in terms of profit, but it should not be given the utmost importance has the only cost relevant components in the organization that can enhance performance. The cost of labour will increase performance but could be detrimental if the money spent on labour is taking a larger percentage of the overall profit component of the organization

Keywords: Cost control: Cost management, Financial performance, Zimbabwe

1.0 Introduction

In pursuit of organizations to attainment or achieve a financial and non-financial goal, the objective of growth maximization and cost minimization cannot be cancelled away in the entire organizational operation in the organization (James and Luke, 2014). Profit maximization is the attainment of the monetary benefit of a company within one financial calendar year. The nemesis of profit maximization is cost minimization because in the pursuit of profit, the cost was continuous and must be managed unless it was lead to loss attainment which leads to the end of the perpetual succession of an organization. This implies the essentials of cost management in an organization (James and Luke, 2014).

Cost management refers to cost cutting and it's commonly approached that firm managers use to respond to the decreasing sustainable profitability (Anderson, 2007). The most important managerial tools are cost management strategies (Zengin and Ada, 2010), and cost management strategies are considered as critical factors to increase revenue for the success of manufacturing companies (Kumar and Shafabi, 2011). Cost management supports decision making and improves competitive advantage that results in better resource allocation (Ellram and Stanley, 2008). In addition, cost management may be an integral feature of overall businesses' management effectiveness and facilitate to determine accurately estimated cost before process starting and can help to forecast cost occurrence in the future. Firms with cost management strategy implementation are able to know when the amount of cost incurred in the future if they have current and future cost information. Thus, managers can make a better decision which positively improved the financial performance of the organization (Caroline, 2014).

Various researches carried out to bring about mixed findings on the relationship between cost management strategies and financial performance. Some argue that cost management is an efficient way of improving the financial performance of a firm while others argue that cost management is old fashioned and based on past information hence it can't on its own greatly impact on the financial performance of a company. A study conducted by Omar (2013) investigating the impact of selected firm characteristics on the financial performance of firms listed under the Agricultural Sector. In his study he measures financial performance using ROA and the study clearly elaborates that a collection of firm characteristics end up affecting the financial performance of manufacturing companies.

A research was done by Ondiek (2010) investigating the relationship between capital structure and financial performance of firms listed at the NSE. She did her analysis using multivariate regression analysis

and used various variables. However in her regression models she established that the firm size and sales growth were positively related to profitability. A research done by Kaplan (1984) stated that measurement systems for today’s manufacturing operations must consider quality, inventory, productivity, innovation and work force. In summary, financial measures which are generated by traditional cost accounting systems provide and inadequate summary of a company’s manufacturing operations. The current global competition requires that non-financial measures such as mentioned previously to be used in the evaluation of a company’s financial performance.

After all developments and changes, in order to survive and make a profit in a globally competitive environment, manufacturing companies have started to question their traditional and cost management systems with the aim of adaptation to global competition and supplying quick-changing demands and expectations of consumers. Traditional cost management and cost plus pricing strategies have also lost their influence in this new competitive environment. Conclusively, based on the inconclusive disposition of researchers this study intends to fill the missing gap between cost control strategies and financial performance of manufacturing companies in Zimbabwe. The study intends to contribute to the enormous literature on the subject-matter. Most importantly, it provides guidelines for academic discussion and also serves as policy assistance for investors and owners of enterprises.

The study is categorized into part one who throws lights on the background of the study as well as the problem statement; part two presents the study’s data and methodology approach, part three displays the results and findings discussion and lastly, part four concludes the study and propose some recommendations.

2.0 Data and Methodology

2.1 Data

The study uses panel data (time series and cross sectional) covering four years (5) from 2014-2018 which was being gathered from the financial statement (Comprehensive income statement and statement of financial position) of the 5 selected manufacturing companies in Zimbabwe. The population of the study consists of all manufacturing firms in Zimbabwe. The sample size consists of five (5) viable manufacturing companies, which have available and quality data for the time period (convenience sampling technique was used). The data for the study was gathered from the financial statement of the firm and other various publications related to the topic. The variables used in the study can be found in table 1 below:

Table 1 Variables description

Variables	Description
Dependent Variable	
ROE	It is profit in an organization which is available for the suppliers of fund or equity. ROE= Return on equity at the time
Independent Variables	
COI	It is the running expenses and overhead cost that is incurred to make sales and income. COI= Cost of Inventories at time
COL	It is the expenses that are expended on labor or man power that aid in the production process COL= Cost of Labor at time
COS	It is the amount of turnover which the manufacturing makes during in a periodic financial year COS= Cost of Sales at the time

2.2 Methodology

The study used panel data methodologies or estimation techniques to analyze the data gathered from the five sampled companies. The panel data is better because it combines both time series and cross sectional data and hence it is expected to give unbiased estimators. The data for this study is a long pool in nature. The method used for the study is fixed and random effect panel regression methods. In the first step, summary statistics of the variables are ascertained to find out the mean, median, skewness, kurtosis and Jarque-bera statistics of the variables. Subsequently, the correlation matrix is computed to check out for multicollinearity, collinearity and order of correlation whether significant or not.

To decide between fixed and random effects, the study conducts a Hausman test, where the null hypothesis requires the preferred model of random effect model against the alternative thus the fixed effect model. However, when the probability level is insignificant (null hypothesis) the random effect is used for the model, but when the probability level is significant (alternative hypothesis) the fixed random effect is used for the model.

2.3 Model Specification

This section presents the model for the study, a mathematical model is constructed to achieve the objective of investigating the impact of cost management and Financial Performance. The study utilizes the panel data sourced from the financial statement of the companies within the period of 2014-2018 (five years). The models below are adapted to suit the study to be able to achieve the study’s objectives (Stephen, Kate and John, 2015).

$$ROE_{i,t} = (\beta_0 + \beta1_{i,t} + \beta2_{i,t} + \beta3_{i,t} + \mu_t).....1$$

In the equation, $\beta1$ to $\beta3$ represents the study’s independent variables thus the cost of labour (COL), cost of inventories (COI) and cost of sales (COS). Moreover, β_0 represents the intercept of the model, i represents the cross-section of the variables and t represents the time period from 2014 to 2017 where μ represents the error term or disturbances that the model cannot estimate. However, ROE is the dependent variables representing the financial performances of the selected companies.

3.0 Empirical findings and results discussion

3.1 Summary statistics

Table 2 Summary statistics of the variables

	ROE	COI	COL	COS
Mean	0.227982	61.15830	17.635289	2.17E+08
Median	0.118647	52.42675	11.545819	1.02E+08
Maximum	1.115897	12.476065	50.37721	9.01E+08
Minimum	-0.026807	15.71420	57.281000	27825194
Std. Dev.	0.279202	38.94541	15.351761	2.53E+08
Skewness	1.871434	0.341684	-1.384555	1.601962
Kurtosis	5.837485	1.565982	3.776707	4.385761
Jarque-Bera	21.14121	2.418258	7.926607	11.67773
Probability	0.000026	0.298457	0.019000	0.002912
Observations	23	23	23	23

The above table depicted the descriptive statistics of the variable used in the study. In the table 2 above ROE (return on equity) has a mean value of 0.22 and a standard deviation of 0.27. ROA (return on asset) has a mean value of 0.05 and a standard deviation of 0.05. The cost of inventories has a mean value of 61.15 and a standard deviation of 38.94. The cost of labour has a mean value of 17.63 and a standard deviation of 15.35. The cost of sales has a mean value of 2.17 and a standard deviation of 2.53. Size has a mean value of 3.30 and a standard deviation of 0.00.

The skeweness of the variable depicts that ROE is positively skewed at 1.87, ROA is positively skewed at 2.21, the cost of inventories is positively 0.34, the cost of sales is positively skewed at 1.60. The cost of labour is negatively skewed at -1.38 and size is negatively skewed at -0.13. The Kurtosis of the variables depicts that ROE is platykurtic at 5.83, ROA is platykurtic at 7.21, and the Cost of inventories is leptokurtic at 1.56. cost of labour is 3.71, cost of sales is platykurtic at 4.38 and Size is leptokurtic at 1.76. The Jarque-Bera statistics ROE is 21.14, ROA is 35.81, the cost of inventories is 2.41, the cost of labor is at 7.92, the cost of sales is 11.67, and size is 1.52.

3.2 Correlation matrix

Table 3 Correlation matrix

	ROE	COI	COL	COS
ROE	1.000			
COI	0.426	1.000		
COL	-0.330	0.072	1.000	
COS	0.114	0.842	0.115	1.000

In table 3, depicts that ROE (return on equity) has a positive correlation relationship with the cost of inventories and cost of sales at 0.42 and 0.11 but negative correlation relationship with the cost of labour at -0.33. ROA (return on asset) has a positive correlation relationship with the cost of inventories and cost of sales at 0.42 and 0.11 and negative relationship with the cost of labour at -0.33.

3.3 Regression results and discussion

3.3.1 Hausman test

Table 4 Hausman test results

Test Summary		Chi-sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq d.f	Prob
Cross-section random		20.607978	3.12	0.0001
Variable	Fixed	Random	Var(Diff)	Prob
COI	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.0543
COL	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.0971
COS	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.0025

The Hausman effect discriminates between the fixed and random effect models in as presented in the table below .The Hausman chi-square 3.12% at 5% is insignificant. Hence it appears there is a correlation between the error term and one or more independent variables. Therefore, the fixed effect model is considered to be capable of generating a more consistent and significant estimate against the random effect model. Therefore, the study’s discussion is based on the fixed effect model.

3.4 Regression analysis with Fixed Effect (Dependent variable- Return on Equity)

Table 5 Fixed effect model

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Error	t-Statistic	Prob
C	3.304519	2.75E-15	1.20E+15	0.000
COI	-1.01E-22	3.24E-22	-0.312556	0.761
COL	-9.48E-23	9.84E-23	-0.963586	0.356
COS	1.72E-23	5.13E-24	3.346291	0.007
Cross-section fixed(dummy variables)				
The period fixed(dummy variables)				
R-squared		1.000	Mean dependent var	3.305
Adjusted R-squared		1.000	S.D dependent var	0.000307
S.E. of regression		1.71E-15	Akaike info criteri	-64.860
Sum squared resid		3.22E-29	Schwarz criteri	-64.268
Log likelihood		757.892	Hannan-Quinn criter	-64.711
F-statistic		6.43E+22	Durbin-Watson stat	
Prob(F-statistic)		0.000		0.620

Table 5 above depicts that the cost of inventories has an insignificant negative impact on the return of equity at 0.05 level of significance for 0.761%. The cost of labour has an insignificant negative effect on return on equity at 0.05 level of significance for 0.3560. The cost of sales has a significant positive effect on the return of equity at the 0.05 level. On the overall regression. The F-statistics value of 6.43 is significant at 5%. Hence, there is evidence that the explanatory variable has an individual and combined effects on the dependent variable.

4.0 Conclusion and recommendation

4.1 Conclusion

The study investigated the effect of cost control on the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Zimbabwe. The specific objectives include examining the cost of inventories, the cost of labour, and the cost of sales on performance. The study will be relevant for investors, management board and regulatory bodies. The study employed a descriptive research design. The study employed panel data covering four (4) years 2014-2018 which was gathered from the financial statement of a selected manufacturing firm. The study employed the fixed effect regression method for its data analysis.

The study revealed that cost of inventories has insignificant negative effect on return on equity, which depicts that cost on inventories have a negative influence of the going concern of the organization in terms of profit, but it should not be given the utmost importance as the only cost relevant components in the organization that can enhance performance. The cost of labour will increase performance but could be detrimental if the money spent on labour as it takes a larger percentage of the overall profit component of the organization. Moreover, the cost of sales showed a positive and significant influence on the profitability or performance of the sampled companies affirming that it is prudent for the organizations to spend to reap profit as in their sales revenue.

4.2 Recommendation

Organizations should ensure well accountable cash or gains are spent on the labour component in order to improve the return on equity for their major shareholders. Again, organizations should spend more on their sales component of the operations; mindfully, prudence should be applied knowing fully well that money or gain spent in this area will be re-coped back through turnover.

References

- i. Anderson, Shannon W. (2007). *Managing Costs and Cost Structure throughout the Value Chain: Research on Strategic Cost Management. Handbook of management accounting research, Elsevier Ltd.*
- ii. Anderson, C., Banke, D., & Janakiraman, N. (2003). *Selling, General, and Administrative Costs Sticky. Journal of Accounting Research 41(1), 47 – 63.*
- iii. Beverley, J. (2002). *ABC vs. TOC: It's a Matter of Time. Management Accounting, 37- 40.*
- iv. Blocher, E., Chen, K. & Lin, T. (1999). *Cost Management: A Strategic Emphasis. The McGraw Hill Companies, Inc., New York*
- v. Drury, C. (2004). *Management and Cost Accounting, Sixth Edition. Thompson Press.*
- vi. Emery, W. & Marques, A. (2011). *The Effects of Transaction Costs, Payment Terms and Power on the Level of Raw Materials Inventories. Journal of Operations Management, 29(1), 236-249.*
- vii. Ellram, Lisa M. & Stanley, Linda L. (2008). *Integrating strategic cost management with a 3DCE Environment: Strategies, practices, and benefits. Journal of purchasing and supply management.*
- viii. Groth, John C. & Kinney, Michael R (1994). *Cost Management and value creation. Management decision.*
- ix. Farrell, J. (1957). *The Measurement of Productive Efficiency. Journal of Royal Statistical.*
- x. Flint, J. (2000). *Improve Internal Reporting with ABC and TOC. Management Accounting, 18-24.*
- xi. King, K., (2008). *The Decomposition of Malmquist Productivity Indexes. Journal of Productivity. 1(1), 3- 4.*
- xii. Hamermesh, S. (1995). *Labour Demand and the Source of Adjustment Costs. The Economic Journal 105 (430): 620-634.*
- xiii. Kallapur, S., & Eldenburg, L. (2005). *Uncertainty, Real Options, and Cost Behavior: Evidence from Washington State Hospitals. Journal of Accounting Research, 2(3):1-5*

- xiv. Luehrman, A. (1998). *Strategy in Constrains Options*. *Harvard Business Review*, September October, 89 – 99.
- xv. Moel, A. & Tufano, P. (2002). *When are Real Options Exercised? An Empirical Study of Mine Closings*. *Review of Financial Studies*. 15 (1): 35-64.
- xvi. Nixon, B. (1998). *Research and Development Performance Measurement: A Case Study*. *Management Accounting Research* 9(3):329–331
- xvii. Pandey, I. M. (1995). *Essentials of financial management*. 4th edition. Vikas Publishing House.
- xviii. Steliaros, E, Thomas, M. & Calleja, K. (2006). *A Note on Cost Stickiness: Some International Comparisons*. *Management Accounting Research*. 17 (1): 127140.
- xix. Zengin, Yasemin & Ada, Erhan. (2010). *Cost Management through product design: Target costing approach*. *International journal of production research*.